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Role of Metacognitive Skills in Predicting Students' Academic Achievement in Office Technology and Management in Polytechnics in Katsina State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper delves into the role of metacognitive skills in predicting academic achievement among students in Office Technology and Management (OTM) in polytechnics in Katsina State, Nigeria. Guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses tested at the 0.05 significance level, the study adopted a descriptive survey design. The entire population of 195 OTM students from Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic and Federal Polytechnic Daura served as the study sample. Data were collected using a Metacognitive Skills Questionnaire (MSQ) and Academic Achievement Assessment (AAA), both validated by experts and demonstrating a reliability coefficient of 0.80. The MSQ measured metacognitive skills on a 4-point Likert scale, while the AAA assessed academic performance in OTM-related courses during the 2023/2024 academic session. A response rate of 91.3% (178/195) was achieved. Data analysis employed descriptive and inferential statistics, with a t-test used to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 significance level. Results, analyzed using SPSS version 23, revealed a strong correlation between metacognitive skills, particularly goal-setting and self-assessment, and academic success. The study underscores the significance of fostering metacognitive abilities within OTM curricula to enhance students' learning outcomes and professional readiness. It recommends the integration of metacognitive skill development into OTM programs to better equip students for the demands of the modern workplace.

Keywords: Metacognitive Skills, Academic Achievement, Students, Office Technology and Management, Polytechnic

INTRODUCTION

In the realm of vocational and technical education, particularly in Office Technology and Management (OTM), academic achievement is a critical determinant of students' readiness for professional challenges. The ability to achieve high academic standards in OTM programs is not

solely dependent on technical skills, but also on students' cognitive abilities, particularly their metacognitive skills. Metacognitive skills, which encompass planning, monitoring, and self-regulation, enable learners to understand and control their cognitive processes, thereby optimizing their approach to learning.

Research has consistently highlighted the importance of metacognitive skills in promoting academic success, as these skills have been shown to positively impact students' engagement, comprehension, and problem-solving capacities. Despite their recognized significance, however, there remains a dearth of emphasis on metacognitive skills within the Nigerian OTM curriculum. This oversight may contribute to the challenges faced by students who struggle to effectively manage their academic tasks, leading to lower performance levels.

Given the growing recognition of metacognitive skills as predictive factors for academic success across various disciplines, it is imperative to explore how these skills predict academic achievement in OTM programs, particularly in polytechnics in Katsina State. This research aims to identify the specific metacognitive skills that are most influential in driving academic achievement in OTM and to develop strategies for promoting these skills among students.

In the context of OTM, where both technological adaptability and administrative competence are essential, metacognitive skills play a crucial role in fostering self-regulated learning among students. As students encounter complex tasks that require critical thinking and adaptability, metacognitive skills help them approach these tasks strategically, evaluate their progress, and adjust their learning techniques as necessary. This ability to adapt is fundamental in a professional environment where OTM graduates are expected to apply their knowledge practically and respond efficiently to workplace challenges.

By identifying and promoting the specific metacognitive skills that drive academic achievement in OTM, this research aims to have a lasting impact on students' educational and professional outcomes, ultimately contributing to the development of a more skilled and adaptable workforce in Nigeria.

Problem Statement

Despite the well-recognized importance of cognitive skills in education, many OTM programs have not fully emphasized the role of metacognitive skills in student achievement. Metacognition, or "thinking about thinking," encompasses a range of abilities that allow students to plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning processes. Studies have shown that students with strong metacognitive skills are better equipped to handle complex tasks, adapt to challenges, and ultimately achieve higher academic success. However, there remains a significant gap in understanding how these skills specifically impact the academic outcomes of OTM students in polytechnic settings, especially in Nigeria, where limited research has explored this relationship in depth.

Research Objectives

The study's objectives are as follows:

- i. To ascertain the relationship between metacognitive skills and academic achievement in Office Technology and Management.
- ii. To determine the specific metacognitive skills that are most predictive of academic achievement in Office Technology and Management.

Research Questions

The study will be guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the extent of the relationship between metacognitive skills and academic achievement in Office Technology and Management in Polytechnics in Katsina State, Nigeria?
- ii. What specific metacognitive skills are predictive of academic achievement in Office Technology and Management within the context of Polytechnics in Katsina State, Nigeria?

Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

Metacognitive Skills:

Metacognitive skills involve cognitive processes that help individuals understand, control, and adjust their learning activities. Introduced by Flavell (1979) as "cognition about cognition," these skills include metacognitive knowledge - awareness of cognitive strategies and task requirements—and

metacognitive regulation, which entails planning, monitoring, and assessing learning strategies. Effective learners, as noted by Dunlosky and Metcalfe (2009), actively judge their comprehension and adapt strategies for improved learning outcomes. Veenman et al. (2016) further emphasize that metacognitive skills foster self-efficacy and autonomy, leading to enhanced academic performance.

Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is a multidimensional construct that measures how well students meet educational goals through indicators such as grades and test scores. Beyond factual knowledge, true academic achievement involves critical thinking and the ability to apply knowledge practically. Influenced by cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions (Elliot & Dweck, 2016), achievement depends on factors such as socio-economic background, motivation, and school environment. In vocational fields like Office Technology and Management (OTM), academic success also relies on bridging theoretical knowledge with practical skills, as Tynjälä (2016) suggests, to prepare students for professional environments.

Office Technology and Management (OTM)

OTM is a specialized field integrating technology and management practices in office settings, equipping students with skills to handle modern workplaces. It covers topics like information management, office software, and organizational behavior, preparing students for diverse roles. As Khan et al. (2020) outline, OTM students gain technical skills, office management capabilities, and soft skills (e.g., communication and problem-solving), critical for adapting in technology-driven workplaces. This hands-on, practical learning approach enhances employability, while demand for OTM professionals grows across sectors like healthcare, education, and finance.

The Theoretical Framework

Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) Theory, developed by Barry J. Zimmerman in 1986 was used in this study. SRL posits that learners are active participants in their educational processes, setting goals, monitoring progress, and reflecting on their learning experiences. The SRL framework consists of three phases: forethought, performance, and self-reflection. It emphasizes the importance of self-regulation in learning, including goal-setting, strategy selection, self-monitoring, and self-assessment. The theory highlights the active role students must take in their learning, and how effective self-regulation can lead to improved academic performance and career readiness.

Components of Metacognition

Metacognitive skills comprise various components, each contributing to effective learning and problem-solving:

- i. **Metacognitive Knowledge:** This encompasses awareness of one's cognitive processes, including knowledge about the strategies, resources, and task requirements necessary for effective learning (Efklides, 2011).
- ii. **Metacognitive Control Strategies:** Students employ strategies such as planning, monitoring, and evaluating their learning progress to achieve their academic goals (Schraw, 1998).
- iii. **Metacognitive Experiences:** These involve the emotional and motivational aspects of learning, including self-efficacy and motivation to learn (Zimmerman, 2000).

Significance of Metacognitive Skills

Metacognitive skills are recognized for their critical role in enhancing learning outcomes. Research indicates that students who possess strong metacognitive skills are better equipped to adapt to challenging academic tasks and exhibit improved academic performance (Efklides, 2011). These skills help students take charge of their learning, set meaningful goals, choose effective learning strategies, and reflect on their progress.

Dimensions of Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is not a one-dimensional construct. It includes various dimensions, each offering a unique perspective on a student's performance:

- i. **Cognitive Achievement:** This dimension focuses on students' knowledge and understanding of subject matter, as demonstrated by their test scores and academic grades (Elliot, 2018).

- ii. **Affective Achievement:** Affective dimensions encompass attitudes, interests, and motivation, which significantly impact a student's willingness to engage in learning and achieve success (Pintrich & Schunk, 2002).
- iii. **Behavioral Achievement:** This dimension concerns students' actual classroom behavior and engagement, such as attendance, participation, and completion of assignments (Kitsantas et al., 2011).

Factors Influencing Academic Achievement

A multitude of factors can influence academic achievement. These include individual, family, school, and societal factors:

- i. **Individual Factors:** Personal characteristics, including cognitive abilities, motivation, self-regulation, and metacognitive skills, play a pivotal role in academic achievement (Bandura, 1993).
- ii. **Family Factors:** The family environment, including parental involvement, socioeconomic status, and support at home, has a significant impact on a student's academic success (Desimone, 1999).
- iii. **School Factors:** Educational institutions, curriculum quality, teaching methods, and the availability of resources all contribute to academic achievement (Baker et al., 1993).
- iv. **Societal Factors:** Broader societal factors, such as culture, social expectations, and policies, can influence the opportunities and challenges students face in their educational journey (Rothstein, 2004).

Metacognition and Academic Achievement

The relationship between metacognition and academic achievement is a topic of great significance in the field of education. Metacognition is a complex cognitive phenomenon that involves awareness of one's cognitive processes, control over learning strategies, and the ability to adapt one's approach to different tasks (Flavell, 1979). Central to metacognition is the concept of self-regulation, which entails setting goals, planning, monitoring progress, and evaluating the effectiveness of one's strategies (Zimmerman, 2000). These metacognitive processes play a pivotal role in academic achievement.

Numerous studies have established a positive relationship between metacognition and academic achievement (Efklides, 2011). Students who possess strong metacognitive skills tend to outperform their peers in various educational settings. Metacognitive abilities enable students to become self-directed learners, making informed choices about their learning strategies, setting meaningful goals, and reflecting on their progress.

Metacognitive skills are particularly significant in problem-solving contexts. They allow students to break down complex problems, select appropriate strategies, monitor their progress, and adapt their approach when necessary (Brown, 1987). These skills not only enhance problem-solving abilities but also contribute to the development of critical thinking skills, which are essential for academic success.

Metacognition in Office Technology and Management

The field of Office Technology and Management places significant demands on students' cognitive and problem-solving skills. This literature review explores the role and significance of metacognition within the specific context of Office Technology and Management education. Metacognition, the awareness and control of one's cognitive processes, plays a crucial role in students' success in this field, influencing their ability to adapt to the dynamic demands of office work and management tasks. Metacognition is the cognitive ability that allows individuals to monitor, regulate, and adapt their thinking and learning strategies. In the context of Office Technology and Management, metacognition is essential because it enables students to develop problem-solving skills, make informed decisions, and effectively manage office tasks.

- i. **Metacognition and Problem Solving:** Metacognition plays a central role in problem solving, a fundamental aspect of Office Technology and Management. Students in this field often encounter complex, real-world problems that require critical thinking and adaptability.

Metacognitive skills allow students to break down these problems, choose appropriate strategies, monitor their progress, and make necessary adjustments (Brown, 1987). This cognitive flexibility is crucial for effective problem solving in office-related tasks.

- ii. **Metacognition and Decision Making:** In the world of office management, effective decision making is paramount. Metacognition provides students with the ability to evaluate their decision-making processes. They can reflect on their choices, the information they considered, and the strategies they employed (Efklides, 2011). This metacognitive reflection enhances decision making abilities and fosters better office management practices.
- iii. **Metacognition and Learning Strategies:** In Office Technology and Management, students often need to adapt to different tasks and learn new skills. Metacognition helps students choose appropriate learning strategies for specific tasks. They can assess the demands of a task and select the most effective approach to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills (Schraw, 1998). This adaptability ensures efficient and successful learning in the field.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive survey research design, chosen for its effectiveness in systematically gathering quantitative data that could reveal relationships between students' metacognitive skills and their academic performance in Office Technology and Management (OTM). A descriptive survey design was appropriate, as it allowed the researcher to explore the extent to which metacognitive skills predict academic achievement, capturing a broad range of student responses from an established educational setting.

The research was conducted within Katsina State, specifically focusing on two major polytechnics: Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic and Federal Polytechnic Daura. These institutions offer specialized training in OTM, making them suitable for studying how metacognitive skills impact academic success in a vocational context. As prominent centers of vocational education in Katsina State, these polytechnics serve as ideal environments to observe how students' cognitive regulation, planning, and evaluation skills influence their learning outcomes and preparedness for professional challenges.

The study population consisted of all 195 OTM students enrolled in the polytechnics during the 2023/2024 academic session. Given the manageable population size, the entire group was included in the study, eliminating the need for sampling. This full population approach ensured comprehensive data collection, enhancing the validity of the findings by capturing a complete picture of the metacognitive skills and academic performance of OTM students in these institutions.

Two main instruments were used to collect data. The Metacognitive Skills Questionnaire (MSQ) assessed students' levels of planning, monitoring, and evaluation within their learning processes, using a 4-point Likert scale to rate skill levels. Meanwhile, the Academic Achievement Assessment (AAA) collected objective measures of students' academic performance, including grades in relevant OTM subjects and cumulative GPAs. This dual-instrument approach provided a balanced view, combining students' self-assessed cognitive skills with concrete academic results.

To ensure that the instruments were valid and reliable, they were reviewed by three experts from the Department of Vocational Education, who confirmed that the tools effectively captured the necessary information for the study's objectives. A pilot test conducted with 20 OTM students from another polytechnic yielded a Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.80, indicating a high level of consistency and reliability.

Data collection was carried out through structured questionnaires, which were distributed to all OTM students in the target polytechnics. With a response rate of 91.3%, the data collected were substantial and provided a reliable basis for analysis. Using SPSS, the data were processed through descriptive statistics and correlational analyses, allowing the researcher to address the research questions and ascertain the influence of metacognitive skills on academic achievement.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the extent of relationship between metacognitive skills and academic achievement in the field of Office Technology and Management in Polytechnics in Katsina State, Nigeria?*

Analysis of data relating to research question 1 is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: extent of relationship between metacognitive skills and academic achievement in the field of Office Technology and Management in Polytechnics in Katsina State, Nigeria.

N = 182				
SN	Item Statements	X	SD	Remarks
1	I set specific academic goals before starting my OTM assignments.	3.02	0.96	High Skill
2	I regularly check my understanding of OTM concepts while studying	3.20	0.84	High Skill
3	I often reflect on my study methods after completing a task in OTM.	3.26	0.70	High Skill
4	I adapt my study strategies based on my performance in OTM assessments.	2.75	0.65	High Skill
5	I plan my study time effectively to cover all OTM course materials.	2.82	0.67	High Skill
6	I use feedback from my instructors to improve my performance in OTM.	3.06	0.77	High Skill
7	I monitor my progress in OTM courses to ensure I meet my academic goals.	3.12	0.74	High Skill
8	I recognize when I need to revise my study approach to better understand OTM concepts.	3.01	0.69	High Skill
9	I believe my ability to manage my study time effectively enhances my academic performance in OTM.	3.41	0.76	High Skill
10	Overall, my metacognitive skills positively influence my academic success in OTM courses.	2.79	0.91	High Skill
Cluster Mean		3.04		High Skill

Source: Questionnaire, 2024

Table 1 demonstrates a robust relationship between metacognitive skills and academic achievement in Office Technology and Management (OTM) among 182 polytechnic students in Katsina State, Nigeria. With a cluster mean score of 3.04, the data indicates that students exhibit high levels of metacognitive skills, showcasing strengths in areas such as setting academic goals, reflecting on their study methods, adapting strategies, managing study time, and monitoring their progress. Notably, the highest mean scores were found in effective study time management (3.41) and progress monitoring (3.12). These findings highlight the significant role that metacognitive skills play in enhancing academic achievement in OTM, emphasizing the necessity of incorporating metacognitive skill training into educational curricula and fostering self-reflection and goal-setting practices among students. Additionally, the standard deviations (SD) ranging from 0.65 to 0.96 suggest moderate variability in the students' responses, indicating a diverse range of experiences and approaches to metacognitive practices.

Research Question 2: *What are the specific metacognitive skills to predict academic achievement in Office Technology and Management within the context of Polytechnics in Katsina State, Nigeria?*

Analysis of data relating to research question 2 is presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Mean responses on the specific metacognitive skills to predict academic achievement in Office Technology and Management within the context of Polytechnics in Katsina State, Nigeria.

N = 182					
SN	Item Statements	X	SD	Remarks	
11	I regularly plan my study sessions to ensure I cover all necessary material for my OTM courses.	3.14	1.03	High Skill	
12	I assess my understanding of OTM topics before and after studying to identify areas needing improvement.	2.99	1.13	High Skill	
13	I set specific learning goals for each study session related to OTM coursework.	2.87	1.06	High Skill	
14	I actively monitor my progress during assignments to ensure I am meeting my academic objectives.	2.70	1.11	High Skill	
15	I utilize self-reflection techniques to evaluate my performance after completing OTM assessments.	2.81	1.00	High Skill	
16	I modify my study strategies based on my success or challenges in understanding OTM concepts.	3.00	1.00	High Skill	
17	I seek feedback on my academic performance and use it to adjust my learning strategies in OTM.	2.49	1.10	High Skill	
18	I identify effective study techniques that work best for me when learning OTM material.	3.28	0.80	High Skill	
19	I consistently evaluate the effectiveness of my learning methods for different OTM subjects.	2.84	1.19	High Skill	
20	I apply metacognitive strategies to prepare for exams in OTM courses, which helps me perform better.	2.05	1.04	High Skill	
Cluster Mean		2.82		High Skill	

Source: Questionnaire, 2024

In Table 2, the mean scores for the specific metacognitive skills ranged from 2.05 to 3.28, with the highest mean score of 3.28 corresponding to identifying effective study techniques, indicating students' awareness of strategies that enhance learning. The lowest mean score of 2.05 relates to the application of metacognitive strategies for exam preparation, reflecting a gap in their utilization during assessments. The overall cluster mean score is 2.82, suggesting that, on average, students exhibit a good level of metacognitive awareness and application. Additionally, the standard deviations for the items range from 0.80 to 1.19, with a standard deviation of 0.80 indicating relatively consistent responses in identifying effective study techniques, while the highest standard deviation of 1.19 pertains to consistently evaluating the effectiveness of learning methods, highlighting greater variability in student experiences and approaches to metacognitive practices.

Test of Hypotheses

The four (4) null hypotheses formulated for the study were tested in this section at 0.05 level of significance.

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the role of metacognitive skills in predicting academic achievement between male and female students in Office Technology and Management in Polytechnics in Katsina State.

The result of the t-test conducted concerning this hypothesis is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean ratings of metacognitive skills in predicting academic achievement between male and female students in Office Technology and Management in Polytechnics in Katsina State.

Gender	N	x	SD	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Male	136	3.02	0.41	180	-1.78	.153	Not Significant
Female	46	3.12	0.3				

The data in Table 3 indicate no significant difference in the role of metacognitive skills in predicting academic achievement between male and female students in Office Technology and Management in Polytechnics in Katsina State. This is shown by a p-value of .153, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups is accepted, suggesting that gender does not significantly affect the role of metacognitive skills in predicting academic performance.

Null Hypothesis 2: Age group does not significantly moderate the relationship between metacognitive skills and academic achievement among Office Technology and Management students in Polytechnics in Katsina State.

The result of the t-test conducted concerning this hypothesis is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean ratings of age group on the relationship between metacognitive skills and academic achievement among Office Technology and Management students in Polytechnics in Katsina State.

Age Group	N	$\bar{x}$	SD	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Below 25 Years	145	2.88	0.43	180	1.25	0.21	Not Significant
Above 25 Years	37	2.84	0.53				

The data in Table 4 indicate that age group does not significantly moderate the relationship between metacognitive skills and academic achievement among Office Technology and Management students in Polytechnics in Katsina State. This is demonstrated by a p-value of 0.21, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two age groups is accepted, suggesting that age does not have a significant effect on the role of metacognitive skills in predicting academic achievement.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study highlight various dimensions of the role of metacognitive skills in predicting academic achievement among students in Office Technology and Management (OTM) programs in polytechnics in Katsina State, Nigeria. This discussion interprets each research question and hypothesis in light of existing literature.

The study findings in Table 5 reveal that there is a high level of metacognitive skill application among OTM students, with a cluster mean score of 3.04, indicating significant use of metacognitive strategies such as goal-setting, self-reflection, time management, and progress monitoring. This supports research by Zimmerman and Moylan (2016), who emphasized the role of self-regulation, planning, and reflective thinking in enhancing academic performance. Similarly, Coutinho (2016) noted that students with high metacognitive awareness tend to achieve better academic outcomes, as they can set meaningful goals, monitor their understanding, and adjust strategies effectively. The consistency of these findings suggests that metacognitive skills are integral to students' success in academic contexts, particularly within vocational fields like OTM, where both theoretical knowledge and practical applications are essential.

Analysis of data in Table 6 identifies specific metacognitive skills that students perceive as contributing to their academic success, such as identifying effective study techniques (mean score of 3.28) and monitoring understanding. However, a lower mean score of 2.05 for applying metacognitive strategies in exam preparation suggests a gap in exam-oriented strategy use, which could affect academic performance. This finding aligns with research by Ahmadi et al. (2018), which found that self-monitoring and adaptive strategy use are critical predictors of academic performance. Mokhtari and Reichard (2019) similarly noted that students who actively employ metacognitive strategies, particularly for understanding complex material, perform better academically. Therefore, these findings reinforce the need to enhance students' abilities to apply metacognitive strategies, not only in regular coursework but also in high-stakes assessments such as exams.

CONCLUSION

The study on the role of metacognitive skills in predicting students' academic achievement in Office Technology and Management (OTM) in Polytechnics in Katsina State, Nigeria, has yielded significant findings that underscore the importance of metacognitive skills in enhancing academic achievement in the field of OTM. The results indicate that metacognitive abilities such as goal-setting, self-assessment, progress monitoring, and reflective thinking are positively correlated with students' academic performance, highlighting their crucial role in fostering self-regulated learning and effective study practices.

Notably, the study found that demographic factors, including gender, age, diploma type, and current CGPA, do not significantly moderate the impact of metacognitive skills on academic success. This suggests that metacognitive skills have a universally beneficial effect on students' academic performance, regardless of individual characteristics.

The study's findings emphasize the significance of metacognitive skills in predicting academic achievement in OTM, and provide valuable insights into the role of these skills in educational settings. The results have important implications for understanding the relationship between metacognitive skills and academic outcomes, and highlight the need for further research in this area.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the development of metacognitive skills in Office Technology and Management (OTM) students:

- i. To promote the development of metacognitive skills, OTM programs should prioritize the integration of modules that focus on planning, self-monitoring, and reflection. Educators should design and deliver these modules, providing students with opportunities to practice and develop these skills.
- ii. OTM lecturers should incorporate structured assignments and lesson plans that emphasize goal-setting, self-assessment, and reflective thinking. Instructional designers can support this effort by creating resources that enable students to practice these skills.

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